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Executive Summary of White Paper (5000 character limit)

We summarize the current state of probing "fundamental physics" using radio pulsars, rotating neutron stars that emit beamed radiation observed as pulses at radio frequencies, as well as key opportunities for Canadian leadership within the next decade. In the context of pulsar astronomy, fundamental physics mainly concerns open questions in gravitational and nuclear astrophysics, such as the validity of general relativity and nature of nuclear physics in extreme-density environments. (Pulsar astronomy and its applications for the detection of gravitational waves is the subject of the standalone White Paper E055.) Several overarching questions that define the field, each of which are subject to active debate in the global radio-astrophysical community, are summarized as follows:

- * What is the equation of state of ultra-dense matter found within neutron stars?
- * What are the minimum and maximum masses of neutron stars? How fast can neutron stars spin? And in what ways do the distributions of neutron star masses and spin periods reflect the physics of compact stars and different formation channels?
- * What is the correct theory of gravitation in the strong-field regime?
- * How can multi-messenger measurements of neutron stars be used to test gravitation and further elucidate the mystery of their structure?

As we discuss in this White Paper for the 2020-2030 Long Range Plan, Canadian scientists are poised to make foundational contributions to the field of pulsar astronomy and its application in studies of fundamental physics. Current and forthcoming radio interferometers developed and built by Canadian researchers are expected to discover and study thousands of pulsars in the Northern sky, most likely including sources in exotic orbital systems. Among these discoveries could be the first pulsars orbiting black holes, whether these black holes are of stellar mass or reside at the center of the Milky Way galaxy, that have long been sought after by observers and theorists alike. The discovery of neutron stars possessing the smallest and largest masses known will place the strongest constraints on viable interior-physics models that are unattainable from laboratory experiment. In order to enable these discoveries, we make the following recommendations:

1. Canada should remain active in the construction, correlator design and implementation for the SKA in a manner that allows for Canadian researchers to take leadership in pulsar science.
2. Funding should be found and allocated to extend the operation of CHIME past its nominal 5-yr observing run. In the context of pulsar science, the extension would provide additional integration times that directly benefit both the pulsar-search and pulsar-timing backends.
3. Broad Canadian support should be provided for the CHORD initiative, which is being designed as a worthy successor to CHIME and its science directives, including pulsar astronomy and its applications to fundamental physics.
4. Canada should consider providing tangible support for the 300-m Arecibo Observatory and 100-m

Green Bank Telescope, two premier facilities that both overcame recent funding struggles. As discussed in the White Paper E055 by I. H. Stairs et al., such support may come in the form of either on-site personnel with scientific and/or technical expertise, instrumentation that further enable breakthrough science at both facilities, or the purchasing of telescope time for measurements related to this topic.

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1 Introduction

Neutron stars represent one of the extreme endpoints in stellar evolution, where the behavior of gravitation and extreme-density nuclear physics within their interiors remain poorly understood. The central density of neutron stars is expected to exceed the nuclear saturation density ($\rho_{\text{sat}} = 2.7 \times 10^{14} \text{ g cm}^{-3}$) by as much as an order of magnitude. Current laboratory measurements do not constrain the behavior of matter at these densities, meaning that a range of "equations of state" (EOSs), which map microphysical interactions to macroscopic quantities, are theoretically possible. Nuclear astrophysics in the context of neutron stars is therefore the subject of active debate (e.g. Özel & Freire, 2016).

Rotating neutron stars are commonly observed as radio pulsars when their emission, beamed along the strong-field magnetic poles, sweeps across the observer's line of sight. Despite lingering mysteries in emission physics, pulsars are nonetheless incredibly useful in probing frontier questions in astrophysics through the timing and "phase connection" of their pulses due to their clock-like rotational stability. It is through pulsar timing that the first evidence for gravitational radiation was found in the "Hulse-Taylor" pulsar-binary system, where long-term timing revealed orbital shrinkage at the rate predicted by general relativity (e.g. Taylor & Weisberg, 1989). As highlighted below, the past decade has seen several important pulsar-based measurements, such as the discovery of massive neutron stars and exquisite tests of general relativity using pulsars in binary/triple systems.

The rise of current and future Canadian instruments with continuous observing capabilities affords an unprecedented view of known pulsars in the Northern hemisphere, as well as potentially lucrative conditions for finding new pulsars in unique environments. Moreover, the forthcoming operation of the Square Kilometre Array (SKA; see White Paper E042) is expected to break new and unprecedented ground with its high sensitivity. These circumstances are favorable for further establishing Canadian leadership in measuring many neutron star masses and testing gravitation through long-term timing of binary pulsars, with the ultimate goal of constraining fundamental physics in extreme environments. In this White Paper for the 2020-2030 Long Range Plan, we highlight future opportunities and address the key questions that propel fundamental-physics studies using radio pulsars forward into the future.

The following discussion is influenced by the case outlined by Fonseca et al. (2019), which was submitted for the 2020-2030 U. S. Decadal Survey for Astronomy & Astrophysics. However, this White Paper expands on additional facets of the science topic, and focuses on the role that Canadian researchers and facilities play in addressing the frontier questions highlighted in the Executive Summary of this White Paper.

2 Mass, EOS Constraints from Pulsar Timing

Pulsar timing is the practice of characterizing all physical phenomena that directly affect the apparent rotation of neutron stars through modeling of pulse arrival times. In the case of binary pulsars, the orbital variations are typically modeled as Keplerian orbits with five orbital parameters; one can then derive the binary mass function, which relates a combination of the *a priori* unknown mass and geometric information of the system with its measured orbital parameters. With sufficient data, it is common to measure deviations from Keplerian motion due to a variety of effects that encode physical information of the system and its components.

For the purposes of this White Paper, the most interesting phenomena occur from point-like particles (e.g., a neutron star and another compact object) interacting in curved spacetime (see Stairs, 2003, for a review). These "post-Keplerian" (PK) effects can either be secular or periodic in nature, and quantify $O(v^2/c^2)$ variations from Keplerian dynamics. Typical PK parameters that are measurable in relativistic binary systems (with orbital periods \sim hours) include the rate of change in the periastron argument of the orbit, the rate of change in the orbital period due to quadrupole-order gravitational radiation, and delays due to a combination of time dilation and gravitational redshift (e.g. Damour & Taylor, 1992).

The relativistic Shapiro time delay (Shapiro, 1964) is a particularly important PK effect and arises due to periodic passage of pulsed emission through spacetime curvature induced by the companion star. In binary-pulsar timing models, the Shapiro delay is a function of two *a priori* unknown parameters, called the "range" (r) and "shape" (s) of the Shapiro delay. In most theories of gravitation, $s = \sin i$ where i is the inclination of the binary

Figure 1: Mass-radius relations for different neutron-star equations of state shown by Özel & Freire (2016); gray lines indicate EOS compositions that are excluded due to inconsistency with the J1614–2230 mass measurement. Horizontal lines indicate large-mass measurements made with high-precision pulsar timing. This figure is reproduced from Fonseca et al. (2019).

system relative to the plane of the sky, while general relativity requires that $r = T_{\odot} m_c$, where $T_{\odot} = GM_{\odot}/c^3$ and m_c is the companion mass. By measuring these parameters, the pulsar mass (m_p) is then immediately determined from the binary mass function. One key advantage of the Shapiro delay is that it can be measured in a pulsar binary system of any size (i.e., the system need not be inherently relativistic), so long as the pulsar yields μs -level timing precision and the combination of m_c and inclination are favorable for significant measurement.

Most of the 43 precisely-measured neutron star masses known to date¹ have come from measurements of the Shapiro delay alone (see Table 2 of Özel & Freire, 2016). Other relativistic effects, such as periastron advance in eccentric binary systems, can be used in conjunction with the Shapiro delay to further improve the mass estimates (see e.g. Freire et al., 2011). Models of the Galactic millisecond-pulsar population predict the number of sub- μs -precision sources increasing by a factor of ~ 5 over the next decade with next-generation radio telescopes (e.g. Lorimer et al., 2019); with dedicated timing of these new sources, the resulting mass measurements will likely number in the hundreds. Such a development is crucial since new individual measurements, especially if extreme, carry significant weight on a variety of compact-object studies. Indeed, prospects for increasing the neutron-star mass population in the near future already look promising with the forthcoming operation of the SKA. Watts et al. (2015) showed that, based on sensitivity projections for SKA1, at least 80% of all Galactic pulsar/white-dwarf binaries with $m_c \geq 0.1 M_{\odot}$ will have measurable Shapiro delay.

2.1 EOS Constraints from Pulsar Masses

Large pulsar masses test the viability of neutron-star equations of state since each EOS differs in its prediction of the maximum mass of neutron stars. Figure 1 displays different EOSs as tabulated by Özel & Freire (2016), along with four of the most massive pulsars known to date: J0348+0432 (Antoniadis et al., 2013); J0740+6620 (Cromartie et al., 2019); J1614–2230 (Fonseca et al., 2016); and J1946+3417 (Barr et al., 2017). The measurement of these pulsar masses, all around $2 M_{\odot}$, eliminates nearly all equation-of-state models with purely strange quark and exotic

¹https://www3.mpifr-bonn.mpg.de/staff/pfreire/NS_masses.html

hadron content. High neutron star masses also constrain the interaction of strange-quark and hadronic matter, as well as the possibility of a phase transition between the two states, in “unified” EOS models that account for both forms (e.g. Baym et al., 2018). Any increase in the observed maximum neutron star mass will more strongly constrain viable equations of state. Such an increase may arise from future observations of the most massive known pulsars and, more importantly, future discoveries of new pulsars.

Low pulsar masses are also important for several reasons. The prediction of minimum neutron star masses varies with the assumed formation channel that produces the observed neutron star (Tauris et al., 2015; Silva et al., 2016); thus the resolution of one or more modes towards the low end of the neutron-star mass distribution likely reflects details in supernova physics that currently remain uncertain (e.g. Stairs, 2004). Moreover, estimates of radii for low-mass neutron stars (e.g. Martinez et al., 2015, 2017) offer the chance to constrain EOS physics at central mass-energy densities near ρ_{sat} , such as the isospin dependence of strong nuclear interactions (e.g. Steiner et al., 2005).

2.2 EOS Constraints from Maximally Rotating Neutron Stars

Realistic EOS models account for the rotation of neutron stars since centrifugal acceleration provides additional support against gravitational collapse and thus allows for even higher masses. In this sense, EOS models for neutron stars have a direct dependence on the fastest pulsar spin periods achievable before break-up of the star. The discovery of “sub-millisecond” pulsars would therefore provide direct constraints on viable EOSs and their predicted maximum masses. Indeed, recent theoretical arguments indicate that the maximum rotational frequency for neutron stars, which use minimal assumptions of EOS microphysics and account for existing $2\text{-}M_{\odot}$ neutron stars, should at least be $\sim 1,200$ Hz (Haskell et al., 2018). Moreover, a range of sub-millisecond pulsar spin periods would help further distinguish neutron stars from quark stars and reflect pulsar-formation channels, since quark stars formed from accretion-induced collapse of white dwarfs can possess spin periods as low as ~ 0.1 ms (Du et al., 2009).

2.3 Neutron-star Moments of Inertia

Mechanical variations of pulsar-binary orbits, such as secular evolution due to spin-orbit coupling, require many decades to resolve due to their smaller perturbations on pulse arrival times (e.g. Damour & Taylor, 1992). However, variations from classical spin-orbit coupling yield unique information about the system, such as the neutron star’s moment of inertia (I_p). Constraints on I_p are highly sought after since they, along with high-precision masses measured from PK effects, characterize internal properties of neutron stars and can be directly measured from pulsar timing (Damour & Schafer, 1988). Lattimer & Schutz (2005), and more recently Raithel et al. (2016), demonstrated that a meaningful constraint on I_p can be directly translated to constraints on the neutron-star radius, despite lingering uncertainties in assumed interior compositions that influence EOS forms. A measurement of both mass and moment of inertia would therefore restrict the allowed phase space in Figure 1 to a finite region, and test the nuclear-astrophysical processes that govern neutron stars in an unprecedented manner.

Due to the high degree of precision needed for this type of measurement, long-term timing of known double-neutron-star (DNS) systems yields the best opportunity for unambiguously constraining models of neutron-star interiors and their corresponding EOSs with measurements of m_p and I_p . Based on data span and arrival-time precision, the DNS systems that will likely yield measurements of I_p in the near future are the double-pulsar system (Kramer et al., 2006), PSR B1534+12 (Fonseca et al., 2014), and PSR J1757–1854 (Cameron et al., 2018). SKA1 is expected to discover ~ 100 DNS systems, and will thus likely provide even more systems where both I_p and m_p can be constrained.

3 Relativistic Gravitation with Pulsars

Tests of gravitation with pulsars invoke self-consistency in predictions among the many PK effects observed in compact DNS systems (Damour & Taylor, 1992). The relativistic “double-pulsar” system, PSR J0737–3039A/B,

currently stands as the best system for tests as timing of the system currently yields seven relativistic timing parameters and up to five tests of general relativity with agreement down to 0.05% accuracy (Kramer et al., 2006). Future discoveries of even tighter orbital systems will further test the validity of relativity theory to PK orders greater than $O(v^2/c^2)$ in the “strong-field” regime that is not accessible with Solar-System experiments.

3.1 Pulsar-Timing Observations of Relativistic Spin Precession

An important relativistic effect that is challenging to constrain is the geodetic precession of the spin angular momentum vector about the total orbital angular momentum vector (Barker & O’Connell, 1975). The rate of relativistic spin precession depends on binary component masses and, if measured, can be used to test relativity theory in conjunction with other PK measurements (e.g. Stairs et al., 2004; Breton et al., 2008). Unlike other PK parameters, the precession rate is more commonly measured through careful analysis of changes in the total-intensity shape and polarization properties of the pulsar signal over time. Relativistic spin precession leads to the eventual and temporary disappearance of the pulsar, though it affords an otherwise unattainable, tomographical view of the pulsar emission cone (e.g. Desvignes et al., 2019).

3.2 Equivalence Principles in the Strong-field Regime

New opportunities in testing gravitational theories have appeared through modeling the dynamics of PSR J0337+1715, a millisecond pulsar that resides within a compact three-body system with two low-mass white dwarfs (Ransom et al., 2014). Recently, Archibald et al. (2018) were able to place a limit on a parameter that quantifies violation of the strong equivalence principle (Δ), such that $|\Delta| < 2.6 \times 10^{-6}$ (with $\Delta = 0$ predicted by general relativity), through careful numerical integration of the relativistic three-body system. This limit on the validity of the strong equivalence principle is the strongest yet obtained through experiment and will improve with observations taken over a long time span.

Moreover, pulsar/white-dwarf binaries with wide component separations are also use for testing equivalence-principle violations through the use of the parametrized post-Newtonian formalism of Nordtvedt & Will (1972). These tests improve with time and the discovery of additional wide-binary pulsars, along with the formulation of additional preferred-frame tests (e.g. Shao et al., 2018)

3.3 Alternative Theories of Gravitation

Existing alternative theories assume both tensor and scalar fields as mediators of gravity, whereas general relativity relies strictly on a tensor-field description. A key prediction from tensor-scalar theories is *dipolar* gravitational radiation in compact binary systems with large differences in component binding energies (Eardley, 1975). Pulsars in relativistic orbits with white dwarfs are natural environments for these tests and have already placed the strongest limits on tensor-scalar theories with constraints on dipolar radiation (e.g. Antoniadis et al., 2012; Freire et al., 2012; Zhu et al., 2019). These constraints significantly improve with increasing pulsar timing baselines so as to further resolve PK variations.

Future improvements to tensor-scalar tests will also come with the discovery of radio pulsars in orbits with stellar-mass black holes. Shao & Li (2018) recently estimated that a small but detectable pulsar/black-hole binary population – between 3 to 80 such systems – resides within the Galactic disk. Future pulsar-search programs, such as those discussed in Section 4 below, are largely motivated by discovering these rare and extreme systems among the Galactic population of observable radio pulsars.

3.4 Unique Opportunities with Galactic-Centre Pulsars

One of the long-sought goals of radio astrophysics is the discovery and timing of radio pulsars in orbit around the supermassive black hole residing in the center of the Milky Way galaxy (e.g. Bower et al., 2018). Simulations have shown that, in such systems, the black-hole mass and spin can be directly estimated from pulsar timing for orbits shorter than 1 yr in period, even if only one pulsar is discovered and yields low timing precision (Liu et al.,

2012). Moreover, the extreme nature of gravitation in the vicinity of the Galactic centre will require unprecedented degrees of accuracy in binary timing models, and will thus yield desirable tests of relativistic gravity to many orders of (v/c) . Furthermore, direct tests of longstanding conjectures in black-hole physics are expected to be possible with measurements of multipole terms of the gravitational potential due to the Galactic-centre black hole along with mass and spin parameters, such as on the validity of the “no-hair” theorem (e.g. Will, 2008).

4 Enabling Constraints on Fundamental Physics with Pulsar Searches

While over 2,600 radio pulsars are known to reside in the Galaxy, projections indicate that the Galactic population should consist of $\sim 10^5$ sources, with a significant fraction possessing sufficient spin orientations for detection on Earth (e.g. Lorimer et al., 2019). The discovery space in pulsar astronomy therefore remains largely unexplored. Among the most anticipated discoveries are pulsars orbiting black holes, due to the unique tests of gravitation in such systems as discussed in Section 3.4. These types of pulsars are expected to possess spin periods ~ 1 s (Shao & Li, 2018). Therefore, while millisecond pulsars are often considered to be the most useful for studies of fundamental physics due to their high rotational stability, future pulsar searching programs should remain flexible to finding sources with a wide range of spin periods (i.e., 0.0001-1 s), degrees of brightness and dispersion properties.

Due to their wide fields of view, target sensitivities and computing designs, current and future Canadian facilities are fully capable of making a large number of pulsar discoveries in the near future. Figure 2 displays the effectiveness of a dedicated searching program with the Canadian Hydrogen Intensity Mapping Experiment (CHIME), using the `PSRPOP` population-synthesis suite (Bates et al., 2014). These simulations consider a population of long-period pulsars and assume a “stacked-spectrum” observing program, where daily periodograms are computed for different positions across the Northern sky and averaged over a 30-day period per position, in order to enhance sensitivity to weak, distance sources. Such a program would yield returns that at least double the Northern pulsar population, owing to the instrument sensitivity and continuous digitization of the CHIME sky. A key advantage of a searching program with CHIME is that these discoveries can then be immediately monitored with the pulsar-timing backend built for CHIME and currently in operation (e.g. Ng & the CHIME/pulsar Collaboration, 2018).

Initial projections made for the Canadian Hydrogen Observatory and Radio-transient Detector (CHORD; see White Paper E029) suggest that the long-period and millisecond-pulsar populations can each be grown by an order of magnitude, though the instrumental parameters that inform the simulations for CHORD remain subject to further refinement. Similar survey-yield estimates have been made for the upcoming SKA1-mid instrument, which is expected to detect at least 9,000 slow pulsars and up to 1,400 millisecond pulsars (e.g. Keane et al., 2015); autonomous observatories like CHIME and CHORD will be able to monitor all Northern-hemisphere discoveries made by the SKA, and make their own discoveries of sources inaccessible to the SKA.

A central assumption in the simulations shown in Figure 2 is the capability of both detecting and characterizing pulsar candidates in near-real time. This is only possible with the development of highly efficient “de-dispersion” algorithms that account for pulse dispersion of broadband signals due to tenuous, ionized plasma that comprises the interstellar medium, as well as analysis pipelines that can handle necessarily large time/frequency-series data. Such a de-dispersion algorithm and detection pipeline are currently in use for real-time detection of fast radio bursts (FRBs) with CHIME (CHIME/FRB Collaboration, 2018). Indeed, the success of the CHIME/FRB (incoherent) de-dispersion algorithm and potential searching returns shown in Figure 2 have motivated the recent funding of a fourth, advanced computing backend for CHIME, that will autonomously search for slow pulsars from the CHIME/FRB data stream during the operation of the experiment. Additional improvements in search-survey yields can be made with the real-time use of “semi-coherent” de-dispersion algorithms that are generalized for searches of accelerated sources, as is the case for relativistic systems (e.g. Smith, 2016; Bassa et al., 2017).

Figure 2: Results of a simulated long-period pulsar search program with CHIME, comparing the spin period (P_s) and dispersion measure (DM) in the simulated CHIME detections (blue, green) to the population of known pulsars found by other observatories around the world (red). The red data of $\sim 2,600$ pulsars were obtained from the ATNF online catalog of pulsar parameters (Manchester et al., 2005). The blue points denote detections made using a coherent spectrum-stacking algorithm, while the green points refer to detections from an incoherent method (where phase information in Fourier-transformed timeseries data are ignored). CHIME is expected to be able to detect at least $\sim 3,000$ long-period pulsars, thus increasing the population in the Northern hemisphere by a comparable amount.

5 Joint Constraints with Multi-wavelength/messenger Observations

Many opportunities will present themselves in the near future for unique constraints on neutron-star structure and tests of gravitation with the forthcoming operation of new observatories across the spectrum, whether it be electromagnetic or gravitational. In all these cases, radio timing measurements provide complementary information about these systems and are oftentimes required to extract the best possible physical constraints from multi-wavelength and/or multi-messenger data:

- For pulsars with masses determined from timing, the constraints on the EOS will be considerably improved when using mass/radius constraints from X-ray missions such as the Neutron Star Interior Composition Explorer (*NICER*). Next-generation X-ray timing experiments, such as the Canadian *Colibrì* mission (see White Papers E048 and E053), will significantly improve such measurements.
- For nearby pulsar binary systems, multi-wavelength observations of white dwarf companions have placed important constraints on pulsar mass estimates through radial velocity measurements (e.g. Antoniadis et al., 2012, 2013). The next generation of ground-based optical telescopes, especially the planned Thirty Metre Telescope (see White Paper E062), will significantly expand the observable volume of white-dwarf companions to radio pulsars and thus heighten the possibility of multi-wavelength constraints on mass and geometric information.
- Observations of gravitational waves from black-hole and neutron-star mergers with the Laser Interferometer

Gravitational Wave Observatory (LIGO), as well as followup electromagnetic observations of LIGO events (e.g., see White Paper E035) are yielding independent tests of gravitation (Abbott et al., 2016). LIGO observations of neutron-star mergers provide complementary EOS constraints that can be combined with results from pulsar timing to further refine EOS constraints (e.g. Abbott et al., 2018).

6 Recommendations

Canadian leadership in radio astronomy is on the brink of a renaissance with the early operation of CHIME, the forthcoming operation of the SKA, and ongoing development for CHORD. In order to facilitate future discoveries with these observatories, certain observational and community-oriented criteria must be satisfied. We provide recommendations that will enable the above science case below, and also provide direct responses to the questions provided by the committee for the Long Range Plan:

- Canada should remain active in the construction, correlator design and implementation for the SKA.
- Funding should be found and allocated to extend the operation of CHIME past its nominal 5-yr observing run. In the context of pulsar science, the extension would provide additional integration times that directly benefit both the pulsar-search and pulsar-timing backends.
- Broad Canadian support should be provided for the CHORD initiative, which is being designed as a worthy successor to CHIME and its science directives, including pulsar astronomy and its applications to fundamental physics.
- Canada should consider providing tangible support for the 300-m Arecibo Observatory and 100-m Green Bank Telescope, two premier facilities that both overcame recent funding struggles. As discussed in White Paper E055, such support may come in the form of either on-site personnel with scientific and/or technical expertise, instrumentation that further enable breakthrough science at both facilities, or the purchasing of telescope time for measurements related to this topic.

1: How does the proposed initiative result in fundamental or transformational advances in our understanding of the Universe?

The nature of gravitation and nuclear astrophysics within the interiors of neutron stars remain unknown and the subject of active theoretical debate. Observations of binary radio pulsars have repeatedly proven to be the best means for testing paradigms with high precision; current and future Canadian observatories are anticipated to be capable of discovering thousands of pulsars and time them with sufficient accuracy, thus opening the pulsar population for unprecedented study.

2: What are the main scientific risks and how will they be mitigated?

From an observational point of view, two common risks in radio-astronomical science are (a) insufficient computing power and (b) terrestrial signals acting as radio frequency interference (RFI). In the case of pulsar-searching strategies outlined in Section 4, an advanced computing cluster is needed for the observing strategies to yield returns similar to those in Figure 2. Thus risk (a) is alleviated with successful funding of the necessary hardware to enable near-real-time pulsar searches, which is the case for CHIME and SKA1. For risk (b), RFI is typically mitigated with offline analyses, though maintaining an ideal RFI environment is a difficult risk with the spreading of telecommunication networks across bandwidths that overlap with those of the proposed instrumentation. It is therefore important to maintain minimal RFI environments at facilities that house current

and future radio instruments.

3: Is there the expectation of and capacity for Canadian scientific, technical or strategic leadership?

Yes. Several Canadian universities are already maintaining internationally renowned research programs in pulsar astronomy and radio-transient science. These groups are leading the development of world-class instruments like CHIME and CHORD, and led the Central Signal Processing design for SKA1. Moreover, these teams will analyze data acquired with CHIME, SKA1 and CHORD that are expected to yield important measurements in the near future.

4: Is there support from, involvement from, and coordination within the relevant Canadian community and more broadly?

Yes. Many of the authors on this White Paper are tenured faculty, senior researchers or postdoctoral researchers based at various Canadian institutions. Moreover, several co-authors listed on this White Paper are based in the United States and across Europe.

5: Will this program position Canadian astronomy for future opportunities and returns in 2020-2030 or beyond 2030?

Yes. As described above, radio pulsars remain a popular and high-impact tool for studying fundamental-physics topics. With few mass measurements and the expectation of many interesting discoveries, this field remains highly sensitive to individual discoveries of physically extreme systems. Facilities like CHIME, SKA and CHORD will make these discoveries in the near future.

6: In what ways is the cost-benefit ratio, including existing investments and future operating costs, favourable?

The cost of constructing backends suitable for pulsar timing are considerably low in comparison to costs for constructing the premier Canadian facilities (and their correlators) described in this White Paper. The prices graphics processing units (GPUs) adequate for pulsar science, necessary components for coherent de-dispersion of pulsar signals, also drop as the GPU market makes further technological advancements. Therefore, adding a GPU-based pulsar timing backend to existing and future instruments is of little comparative cost, low risk and high scientific reward.

7: What are the main programmatic risks and how will they be mitigated?

The main programmatic risk is that Canadian facilities do not find pulsars in more extreme conditions, such as orbiting the Galactic-centre supermassive black hole or pulsars possessing masses greater than the current value found by (Cromartie et al., 2019). However, given that a tiny fraction of the expected observable pulsar population has been detected so far, we are confident that many more breakthrough discoveries await us. Furthermore, even if Canadian facilities do not make these pulsar discoveries, pulsar backends built for CHIME, CHORD and the SKA can study their timing properties and make unique measurements of strong-field effects that perturb their orbits.

Another risk is the closing, or lessening of “open skies” time, of other premier facilities in North America, especially the Arecibo and Green Bank observatories. This risk can be mitigated with the purchasing of telescope time for observations of particularly interesting radio pulsars, which is currently being done by the North American Nanohertz Observatory for Gravitational Waves (which includes Canadian members) for

gravitational-wave detection.

8: Does the proposed initiative offer specific tangible benefits to Canadians, including but not limited to interdisciplinary research, industry opportunities, HQP training, EDI, outreach or education?

The technical skills acquired in the study of signal processing and data analysis, the key abilities required for the work described in this White Paper, are generally transferable to other non-astronomical fields of similar technical rigour. The extreme nature of neutron stars and pulsars make them appealing for engaging a general, public audience via outreach activities. The large data volume from ongoing and future pulsar-search surveys also lead to potentially rewarding ventures into citizen science.

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